

Semantically Enriched Web Usage Mining for Personalization

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Abstract : The continuous growth in the size of the World Wide Web has resulted in intricate Web sites, demanding enhanced user skills and more sophisticated tools to help the Web user to find the desired information. In order to make Web more user friendly, it is necessary to provide personalized services and recommendations to the Web user. For discovering interesting and frequent navigation patterns from Web server logs many Web usage mining techniques have been applied. The recommendation accuracy of usage based techniques can be improved by integrating Web site content and site structure in the personalization process. Herein, we propose Semantically enriched Web Usage Mining method for Personalization (SWUMP), an extension to solely usage based technique. This approach is a combination of the fields of Web Usage Mining and Semantic Web. In the proposed method, we envisage enriching the undirected graph derived from usage data with rich semantic information extracted from the Web pages and the Web site structure. We conducted extensive experimental evaluation on two real world datasets and on one partially generated synthetic dataset. The results obtained on both real-world and synthetic data show that the SWUMP generates accurate recommendations and is able to achieve 10-20% better accuracy than the pure usage based model. The SWUMP addresses the new item problem inherent to solely usage based techniques.

Keywords : Prediction, Recommendation, Semantic Web Usage Mining, Web Usage Mining

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014